

Calculation of b^* of Laidler and Landskroener Equation for General Ion-Dipole Type of Reactions in Solutions and its Application

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The Laidler and Landskroener method for evaluating b^* , the distance of closest approach of solvent molecules to the activated complex in a bimolecular reaction is applicable only when the transition state is highly polarized. A more general method for calculating b^* in case of above mentioned reactions, irrespective of the polarity of the transition state and free from any assumptions about the model of the activated complex, has been suggested. The method has been applied in alkaline hydrolysis of ethylacetate in water enriched DMSO between 30 and 35°. The b^* was found to be 2.41 Å which is in agreement with the value obtained from the data of D. D. Roberts.

AMONG the various theoretical expressions, relating rate constant with the properties of solvents and reactants, the Laidler and Landskroener equation¹ is most widely accepted. The equation for ion-dipole type of bimolecular reaction in solutions in which the transition state is much more polarized than the initial state, can be expressed as follows;

$$\log k = \log k_0 + \frac{1}{2.303} \frac{e^2}{2kT} \left(\frac{1}{b_A} - \frac{1}{b^*} - \frac{3G^*}{2b^{*3}} \right) \frac{1}{D} + \frac{1}{2.303} \frac{e^2}{2kT} \left(\frac{1}{b^*} - \frac{1}{b_A} + \frac{3G^*}{4b^{*3}} \right) \quad (1)$$

The applicability of the above equation has been tested by Laidler and Landskroener themselves by calculating the value of b^* for several ion-dipole type of bimolecular reactions yielding a negative slope for $\log k$ against $\frac{1}{D}$. The method of computation of b^* as well as G^* has been refined and simplified by proposing a pair of equations by the authors of these lines in their previous communication². However, the computation suffers from an arbitrary assumption about the dielectric constant of ideal solution and the equations have not been applied for those ion-dipole type of reactions in which a linear relationship of $\log k$ against $\frac{1}{D}$ yields

a positive slope. Therefore the present work is undertaken with a view (i) to propose an equation for the variation of specific rate constant for an ion-dipole type of bimolecular reactions in which the transition state may or may not be polarized and the slope of $\log k$ against $\frac{1}{D}$ may be positive or negative, (ii) to develop a new method for computation of b^* , the distance of closest approach of solvent molecules to the transition state, in which no assumption about the dielectric constant of ideal solution is needed, and (iii) to test the applicability of the proposed equation in cases where

a plot of $\log k$ against $\frac{1}{D}$ results in a straight line with positive slope.

With increasing researches on solvent effect it is now clearly recognised that the action of non-aqueous component of a mixture is more than simple diluent or modifier of its dielectric properties. Recently, it has been reported³ that DMSO as a cosolvent of water leads to a breakdown of water-water interactions forming an intermolecular association with it. Wolford⁴ on the basis of kinetic studies in DMSO-water mixtures concluded that the mixtures can be divided into three regions, molefraction of DMSO varying from 0-0.3, 0.3-0.45 and 0.45-1.0. Prior to above reporting D. D. Roberts^{5,6} studied the alkaline hydrolysis of ethylacetate in DMSO-water mixture in the Wolford's second region of the mixture, obtaining a positive slope for the variation of $\log k$ against $\frac{1}{D}$. Therefore the authors selected to study the same reaction but in the first region of DMSO-water mixture in order to explore the pronounced specific effects of the solvent mixture if any and to apply the data thus obtained in the evaluation of b^* of Laidler-Landskroener equation. It would seem to the authors that in this region the size of the ions would be nearly of the same dimension as in water alone.

Experimental

Standard solutions of NaOH (0.05 M) and ethylacetate (0.033M) were prepared in solvent mixture of A. R. grade DMSO varying from 5-25% in double distilled water. The above solutions in a particular solvent composition were thermostated in a bath controlled within $\pm 0.5^\circ$. After mixing equal volume of both the solutions, the kinetics of the reaction were followed by removing 10 ml of liquid from the reaction mixture at different intervals of time and adding it to a

known excess of standard ice cold HCl solution, the excess of which was estimated with standard baryta solution. Reproducible results were always obtained. The specific rate calculated in various solvent mixtures at 30.2° and 35° are shown in table 1. The table also includes the dielectric constant values extrapolated from the curve using the data of Wolford⁴. Akerlof's equation⁷ was used for changing the values to different temperatures.

TABLE 1—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANTS IN WATER—DMSO MIXTURES

Solvent composition % (v/v) of DMSO	K, specific rate constant at		Dielectric constants of solvent mixtures at	
	30.2°C	35°C	30.2°C	35°C
5	7.17	11.15	76.43	74.73
10	7.58	12.01	76.33	74.63
15	7.95	12.46	76.17	74.50
20	8.52	12.68	76.00	74.30
25	9.04	13.76	75.80	74.05

Discussion

The Laidler-Landskroener equation is based on the assumption that the change in the solvent composition results in the change of activity coefficient. The activity coefficient expression for Zwitter ions in a solution has been given by Kirkwood^{8,9} which may be expressed as follows, if the dielectric constant of the solute is taken into account.

$$\ln \gamma = \frac{e^2}{2kT} \left[\frac{1}{D} \left\{ \frac{Z^2}{b} + \frac{3G}{2b^3} \right\} - \left\{ \frac{Z^2}{b} + \frac{3G}{2(1+\alpha)b^3} \right\} \right] \quad (2)$$

where, G is a number depending on the distribution of charges and proportional to dipole moment and α is half of the dielectric constant of solute. The other terms have their usual significance.

For a bimolecular reaction of type

in solution, rate coefficient is expressed as

$$\ln k = \ln k_0 + \ln \frac{\gamma_A \gamma_B}{\gamma_{AB^*}}$$

Similarly, using equation (2) for an ion-dipole type of bimolecular reaction, following the method of Laidler and Landskroener, one can express :

$$\lg k = \lg k_0 + \frac{1}{2.303} \frac{e^2}{2kT} \left[\left\{ \left(\frac{1}{b_A} - \frac{1}{b^*} + \frac{3}{2} \sum \frac{G}{b^3} \right) \frac{1}{D} \right\} - \left\{ \frac{1}{b_A} - \frac{1}{b^*} + \frac{3}{2(1+\alpha)} \sum \frac{G}{b^3} \right\} \right] \quad (3)$$

$$\text{where } \sum \frac{G}{b^3} = \left(\frac{G_A}{b_A^3} + \frac{G_B}{b_B^3} - \frac{G^*}{b^{*3}} \right)$$

and it is proportional to the change in the polarization of the reactants due to formation of the transition state. Expressing equation (3) in a more general form,

$$\log k = \log k_0 + \frac{X}{TD} + \frac{Y}{T} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where } X = \frac{1}{2.303} \frac{e^2}{2k} \left(\frac{1}{b_A} - \frac{1}{b^*} + \frac{3}{2} \sum \frac{G}{b^3} \right)$$

$$\text{and } Y = -\frac{1}{2.303} \frac{e^2}{2k} \left(\frac{1}{b_A} - \frac{1}{b^*} + \frac{3}{2(1+\alpha)} \sum \frac{G}{b^3} \right)$$

Rearranging the expressions for X and Y and putting

$$A = \frac{1}{2.303} \frac{e^2}{2k}, \text{ we get}$$

$$\frac{1}{b_A} - \frac{1}{b^*} + \frac{3}{2} \sum \frac{G}{b^3} = \frac{X}{A} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{and } \frac{1}{b_A} - \frac{1}{b^*} + \frac{3}{2(1+\alpha)} \sum \frac{G}{b^3} = -\frac{Y}{A} \quad (6)$$

subtracting equation (6) from (5)

$$\frac{3\alpha}{2(1+\alpha)} \sum \frac{G}{b^3} = \frac{X+Y}{A} \quad (7)$$

substituting the value $\sum \frac{G}{b^3}$ in equation (5) the desired

expression is obtained as follows :

$$\frac{1}{b_A} - \frac{1}{b^*} = \frac{1}{A} \left[X - \frac{1+\alpha}{\alpha} (X+Y) \right] \quad (8)$$

The value of X can be obtained from the slope of $\log k$ against $\frac{1}{D}$ and the mean value of Y between two temperatures close to the experimental temperature can be determined from the expression,

$$\log \frac{k_1}{k_2} = \left(\frac{X_1}{D_1 T_1} - \frac{X_2}{D_2 T_2} \right) + Y \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right) \quad (9)$$

the terms with subscript 1 and 2 represent their values at temperatures T_1 and T_2 .

In case of alkaline hydrolysis of ethylacetate in water enriched DMSO, the graph of $\log k$ against $\frac{1}{D}$ was found to be linear and the value of $\frac{X}{T}$ at 30.2° and 35° calculated from the slope were 905.5 and 651.5 respectively. The values of Y between 30.2 and 35°

evaluated with the help of equation (9) are shown in table 2. The size of OH^- ion (b_A) in aqueous medium was calculated to be $3.69 \text{ \AA}^\circ$ from its molar volume¹⁰ and the size of H_3O^+ ion in water.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF X, Y AND b^* IN WATER-DMSO MIXTURES

Composition of solvent in %(v/v)	Values of Y	Value of $\frac{X}{T}$ at 30.2°C	b^* in A° at 30.2°C
5	-64,710		2.41
10	-64,680		2.41
15	-64,860	905.5	2.45
20	-64,550		2.39
25	-64,680		2.41

Thus using the values of $\frac{X}{T}$, mean Y, and b_A the values of b^* were calculated with the help of equation (8) at 30.2° as reported in table 2. The average value of b^* comes to $2.415 \text{ \AA}^\circ$. The value of b^* was also calculated from the data of D. D. Roberts⁶ using the equation (8) at 25° , which was found to be $2.02 \text{ \AA}^\circ$. The b^* value could not be calculated at 30.2° from the data of Roberts due to lack of sufficient data. However, the agreement with our value is quite good considering the difference in temperature and that of the solvent composition.

According to the Kirkwood theory^{8,9} these radii should not correspond to the overall radii, but should be effective radii related to the size of the active groups in the complex molecules. Therefore the essential factor is the closeness of approach of the solvent molecules to the seat of reactions. It is quite possible that the solvent sheath over the OH^- ion present in the bulk is removed in the transition state and similar to the spreading of the charge, the solvent sheath too spreads over the transition state. Again, the solvation of the transition state will be much less in comparison to reactant ion due to the decrease in the charge density. As the size of the bare OH^- ion is $1.4 \text{ \AA}^\circ$ the effective size of the transition state species, defined as the distance of closest approach of a solvent molecule to the seat of reaction, found to be $2.415 \text{ \AA}^\circ$ is not unreasonable.

The distance of C-O bond reported¹³ is of the order $1.43 \text{ \AA}^\circ$. Therefore it is quite reasonable that the new C... OH^- bond which is being formed in the transition state due to the attack of OH^- ion on the carbonyl group of the ester may lie between 2 to $3 \text{ \AA}^\circ$ in case of simple ester hydrolysis. Thus the method proposed for evaluating b^* , which is a very important parameter for predicting solvent effect, appears to be quite convincing. And as the method is more general and simple, its applicability is greatly increased. In ion dipole type of reactions with transition state less polarized or with reverse polarity the Laidler-Landskroener method can not be applied for calculating b^* , where as the method suggested in the article can be applied satisfactorily to calculate b^* even in those cases. However, further investigations are in progress to apply the method suggested in various types of ion-dipole reactions in solution in different solvent mixtures.

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References

1. K. J. LAIDLER and P. A. LANDSKROENER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, 52, 200.
2. R. C. JHA, LALLAN SINGH and S. N. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 657.
3. M. D. ZEIDLER in "Water—A comprehensive Treatise" (Ed.) F. Franks, Plenum Press, 1973, Vol. 2, p. 564.
4. R. K. WOLFORD, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, 68, 3392.
5. D. D. ROBERTS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, 29, 2039.
6. D. D. ROBERTS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, 31, 4037.
7. G. AKERLOF, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 4125.
8. J. G. KIRKWOOD, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1934, 2, 351.
9. J. G. KIRKWOOD and F. H. WESTHEIMER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1938, 6, 506.
10. F. J. MILLERO, *Chem. Rev.*, 1971, 71, 162.
11. R. A. ROBINSON and R. H. STOKES, "Electrolyte Solutions", Butterworths, London, 1966, p. 357.
12. "A hand book of Chemistry and Physics" (Ed.) C. N. R. RAO, East-West Press, New Delhi, 1967, p. 227.